

Hello, I am <<investigator name>>, <<role>> at the <<Anonymous>>.

<<if more investigators>>

I am accompanied by my supervisor, <<name>>, <<role>> at the <<Anonymous>>.

<<end>>

Thank you very much for taking part in this study.

I hope you have gone through the information sheet.

<<if not>>

please take some time to go through it.

<<end>>

Before starting off, I would like you {all} to know that this {interview/focus group} is being audio recorded.

And after transcribing is done, this audio recording will be deleted.

Also please know that there are no right or wrong answers, we are just looking for your perspective.

Hope you {all} are comfortable with everything and would like to start with the interview?

Topic: Participant demographics.

- job role.
- day to day activities.

Topic: Challenges in day-day activities.

- <<if no challenges>>
 - Prompt: these challenges could be anything, from coding to time management, work pressures.
- <<if challenges related to sustainability>>
 - Prompt: These challenges don't necessarily be due to sustainability. They could be personal to your work as well.
- Resolve steps, if any.

Topic: Awareness on sustainability concepts.

- Gained this knowledge from? Studies? Self-study? UN SDGS? Any frameworks?
- <<If yes for studies>>
 - which course and university.
 - part of curriculum or instructor's interest?

Topic: Sustainability meaning.

- In general
- Sustainable software engineering

Topic: Awareness on organisation's sustainability efforts.

- View of participants towards these efforts?

Topic: Current sustainable practices in participant's role.

- Mandated or voluntary.
- Challenges.

Topic: Organisation's priority towards sustainable SE.

- Should be prioritized, yes, or no? why?

Topic: Benefits from sustainable SE.

- Organisational.
- SE teams.

<<if not practicing currently>>

Topic: Challenges from sustainable SE.

- Organisational.
- SE teams.

<<end>>

Topic: Stakeholders for sustainable SE.

Topic: Dedicated team for sustainable SE practices.

That is all for this {{interview/focus group}}.

Thank you very much for your time and your answers.

Do you have any questions to ask?

Once again thank you very much for taking part in this study.

Have a good day!